

Dihydroisocoumarins. Part XI. Synthesis of 3,4-Dihydro-7-methoxyisocoumarin and its Transformation to 7-Methoxyisocoumarin

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3,4-Dihydro-7-methoxyisocoumarin (VII), prepared by two alternative routes, has been transformed to 7-methoxyisocoumarin (IX) with the aid of *N*-bromosuccinimide.

3,4-Dihydro-7-methoxyisocoumarin (VII) has been synthesised by two different routes. In one, the method reported in earlier papers^{1,2} of this series was adopted. Methyl 2-methoxycarbonyl-4-methoxyphenylacetate³ (II) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride and the resulting homophthalyl alcohol (IV) was dehydrated with fused acid potassium sulphate to 7-methoxyisochroman (V). Subsequent oxidation with chromium trioxide provided a complex mixture of reaction products from which we were unable to isolate the dihydroisocoumarin (VII), whereas selenium dioxide oxidation afforded products, which required extensive purification for the isolation of (VII) in 20% yield. The low yield in this instance, in contrast to other cases^{1,2} of such oxidation of isochromans, may be attributed to the lack of activation of the methylene group at 1-position in the isochroman (V) owing to the unfavourable orientation of the electron-releasing methoxyl group. This is in keeping with our previous observation⁴ that such a factor does adversely affect the oxidation of 5,7-dimethoxyisochroman to 3,4-dihydro-5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin.

1. Srivastava and Chaudhury, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 4337.
2. Mukhopadhyay and Chaudhury, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 433.
3. Robertson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3375.
4. Srivastava and Chaudhury, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 805.

In view of the low yield of the dihydroisocoumarin (VII) by the preceding method, we undertook its synthesis by another alternative route. Recently a shorter and superior route has been reported⁵ from this laboratory, which involves methanolysis of homophthalic anhydrides to furnish exclusively the half-esters, *o*-carboxyphenylacetates, and their subsequent reduction with lithium borohydride to dihydroisocoumarins. Following this sequence of reactions, methanolysis of 4-methoxyhomophthalic anhydride (VI), prepared by the action of acetyl chloride on 4-methoxyhomophthalic acid⁶ (I), furnished methyl 2'-carboxy-4-methoxyphenylacetate (III) in almost quantitative yield. Reduction of the half-ester with lithium borohydride afforded 3,4-dihydro-7-methoxyisocoumarin (VII) in 63.4% yield along with 4-methoxyhomophthalyl alcohol (IV) in 24.6% yield. The formation of the homophthalyl alcohol (IV) as a reduction product in this case is noteworthy since lithium borohydride normally has no action on aromatic carboxylic acids⁷. Moreover, in other instances⁸ of such reduction, lithium borohydride did not affect the carboxyl group of *o*-carboxyphenylacetates but selectively reduced the ester group, yielding *o*-carboxyphenethyl alcohols, which lactonised *in situ* to furnish the corresponding dihydroisocoumarins as the sole product.

3,4-Dihydro-7-methoxyisocoumarin (VII) was next converted into 7-methoxyisocoumarin (IX)⁹ by the method of Srivastava and Chaudhury¹. Reaction with NBS provided 4-bromo-3,4-dihydro-7-methoxyisocoumarin (VIII) which, on dehydrobromination with refluxing triethylamine, furnished 7-methoxyisocoumarin (IX).

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Hydroxymethyl-4-methoxyphenethyl Alcohol (IV).—To a stirred slurry of LiAlH_4 (1.5 g.) in dry ether (100 ml) was added, at such a rate as to maintain reflux, a solution of the homophthalate³ (II, 4g.) in dry ether (50 ml). After refluxing for 2 hr., water was added cautiously with stirring, followed by $2N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ to produce a clear solution. The ether layer was separated, the aqueous solution extracted with ether (40 ml $\times$ 10), and the combined extract dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent left a colorless liquid, which soon solidified. Recrystallisations from ethyl acetate-light petroleum furnished the pure alcohol as colorless elongated prisms (2.5 g., 81.9%), m.p. 97°. (Found: C, 66.22; H, 7.91. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 65.94; H, 7.69%).

7-Methoxyisochroman (V).—A mixture of the above homophthalyl alcohol (IV, 1.5 g.) and freshly fused KHSO_4 (2 g.) was heated for 1½ hr. at 130–140° in an oil bath, the system being connected to an efficient water pump, when most of the water distilled. The residue was next distilled under vacuum to yield the product (V) as a colorless oil (1.7 g., 90.6%), b.p. 94–95°/11.15mm. (Found: C, 73.25; H, 7.44. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 73.18; H, 7.32%).

5. Bose and Chaudhury, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, **20**, 49.

6. Desai and Usgaonkar, *this Journal*, 1963, **40**, 239.

7. Gaylord, "Reduction with Complex Metal Hydrides", Interscience, 1956, Table VI, p. 102.

*All m.p.s are uncorrected. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60–80°. Microanalyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

4-Methoxyhomophthalic Anhydride (VI).—4-Methoxyhomophthalic acid⁶ (I, 15 g.) in acetyl chloride (105 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 3½ hr. and then the mixture of acetyl chloride and acetic anhydride was distilled under reduced pressure. The pale yellow solid residue was taken up in dry ether, filtered, and washed thoroughly with dry ether. It was crystallised from benzene-light petroleum to furnish the anhydride as pale yellow needles (11.6 g., 83.6%), m.p. 143-44°. Further purification by vacuum sublimation (bath temp. 120-25°/2 mm) furnished the analytical specimen as colorless needles, m.p. 145-46°. (Found: C, 62.71; H, 3.84. $C_{10}H_8O_4$ requires C, 62.4; H, 4.1%).

Methyl 2-Carboxy-4-methoxyphenylacetate (III).—The preceding anhydride (5 g.) in absolute methanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr. The crystalline solid residue, left after the distillation of methanol, was purified by crystallisation from ethyl acetate-light petroleum to furnish the pure half-ester (III) as colorless prismatic needles, m.p. 112-13°, in almost quantitative yield. (Found: C, 59.55; H, 5.16. $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 59.3; H, 5.3%).

3,4-Dihydro-7-methoxyisocoumarin (VII): *Method (a)*.— $LiBH_4$ (0.5 g.) was added to a solution of the half-ester (III, 2.5 g.) in dry THF (50 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 3 hr. The solvent was next distilled and the complex decomposed by careful addition of ice-cold water, followed by 2*N*- H_2SO_4 , until a clear solution was obtained. It was extracted with chloroform (3 × 25 ml) and the extract washed repeatedly with aqueous bicarbonate. The combined bicarbonate solution after acidification with 2*N*- H_2SO_4 was extracted with chloroform (3 × 20 ml) and the extract dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent left an oil, which on distillation *in vacuo* afforded (VII) as colorless liquid (1.23 g., 63.4%), b.p. 167-68°/3 mm. It solidified on keeping in an ice chest as colorless needles, m.p. 38-39°. (Found: C, 67.57; H, 5.76. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 67.42; H, 5.62%).

The chloroform solution, left after washing with aqueous bicarbonate, was dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent evaporated to afford a gum, which solidified on standing. Recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-light petroleum yielded the pure homophthalyl alcohol (IV) as elongated prisms (0.5 g., 24.6%), m.p. 97°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained as above.

Method (b).—A solution of the isochroman (V, 1.5 g.) in dry xylene (20 ml) was refluxed with SeO_2 (1.5 g.) for 6 hr. At the end of this period, SeO_2 (0.7 g.) was again added and the reflux continued for a further period of 6 hr. The xylene solution was filtered and evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The residue was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed through a column of Brockmann alumina, which was eluted with the same solvent. Evaporation of benzene left an oil, which was distilled *in vacuo* to furnish, after a forerun of the isochroman, 3,4-dihydro-7-methoxyisocoumarin (VII) (0.33 g., 20.5%), b.p. 167-68°/3 mm. On cooling and being nucleated with the specimen obtained under method (a), it solidified to colorless needles; m.p. and mixed m.p. 38-39°.

4-Bromo-3,4-dihydro-7-methoxyisocoumarin (VIII).—A mixture of the dihydroisocoumarin (VII, 1.2 g.), NBS (1.44 g.) and benzoyl peroxide (0.024 g.) in CCl_4 (30 ml) was refluxed for 1 hr. close to an illuminated 60-watt lamp. More benzoyl peroxide (0.22 g.) was added and the reflux continued for 1 hr. The cooled solution was filtered from succinimide which was washed with CCl_4 . The combined filtrate and washings were washed with 10% Na_2CO_3 and water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent left a solid, which on several crystallisations from ethyl acetate-light petroleum furnished the pure bromo compound

(VIII) as colorless rectangular prisms (1.2 g., 70.5%), m.p. 136-37°. (Found: C, 46.9; H, 3.2; Br, 30.85. $C_{10}H_9O_3Br$ requires C, 46.6; H, 3.5; Br, 31.13%).

7-Methoxyisocoumarin (IX).—The preceding compound (0.45 g.) in triethylamine (15 ml) was refluxed for 18 hr. and the brown solid residue, obtained after evaporation of triethylamine, was repeatedly triturated with ice-cold 2*N*-HCl, followed by water. It was collected, dried, and purified by vacuum sublimation (bath temp. 115-20°/1.5 mm) to afford colorless crystals. Subsequent recrystallisations from chloroform-light petroleum yielded the pure isocoumarin (IX) as prismatic needles (0.22 g., 70%), m.p. 108° (lit.³ m.p. 108-109°). Since the pure isocoumarin gave positive Beilstein test, several recrystallisations were necessary to obtain an analytical specimen, the m.p. remaining unchanged. (Found: C, 68.37; H, 4.26. Calc. for $C_{10}H_8O_3$: C, 68.19; H, 4.54%).

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